

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Geological survey of the Fiumarella di Corleto hydrographic basin

SPOKE 4 – Summer

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A) Geological survey of the Fiumarella di Corleto hydrographic Basin

Geolithological and geophorphological data of the area enclosed in the morphological limit of the Fiumarella di Corleto catchment area are reported below.

Introduction

The Fiumarella di Corleto catchment is located in the southern Apennines to north of the a tectonic boundary between the Miocene Gorgoglione and Pliocene-Quaternary Sant'Arcangelo units, along the western boundary of the Gorgoglione Formation (fig. 1). Such tectonic boundary is a N 120 trending structure with Quaternary lefttransensional movement known as the Scorciabuoi Fault (Casciello et al., 2022). The cathment area is on the raised side of the fault.

Fig. 1 - a) Location of southern Apennines; **b)** Schematic geological map of the southern Apennines and location of figure 3.

The valley has a V-shaped topographic profile (fig. 2) and a thalweg, filled with landslide material and coarse-grained sediments made of sandy clay with angular metric blocks of sandstone and calcarenite.

The geological characteristics above described suggest for the Fiumarella di Corleto catchment a territory subject to erosion with prevalent mass transport of muddy sediment with angular clasts and metric blocks, located in a tectonic uplift area.

Fig. 2 – Orthophoto and topographic profile of the Fiumarella di Corleto catchment.

From the point of view of human activities, in the basin subtended by the Fiumarella di Corleto there are, on the left side of the valley, n. 3 oil wells (labeled: Tempa Rossa 1, Tempa Rossa 2 and Total pozzo 1 Guardia Perticara) and the Total Corleto Perticara loading center. Then, on the right side, in correspondence with the watershed, there is the town of Corleto Perticara and

throughout the basin there are numerous isolated agricultural houses and communication routes often interrupted by hydrogeological instability phenomena.

In this paper, in order to define the geological factors active in the study area, we performed a stratigraphic-sedimentological research throughout the catchment area and localized detailed geomorphological analyses.

Methods and techniques

Geological surveys were conducted on 1:10,000 scale maps of the Regional Technical Cartography (CTR Regione Basilicata), available online (<http://rsdi.regione.basilicata.it/web/quest/home>). Physical-stratigraphy and facies analysis were applied to several stratigraphic sections in order to define the nature of the unit boundaries, their stratigraphic relationships (vertical and lateral), and the sedimentological characteristics of the deposits. Satellite (Google Earth Pro) photos were analysed in order to identify the main morphostructural features and the Quaternary cover. Using the Digital Terrain Model at different resolutions (5 m and 1 m) it was possible to carry out calculations on the acclivity and exposure of the area included in the Fiumarella di Corleto catchment. In order to analyze the vegetation status and water content of the study area, NDVI and NDMI from 2015 to 2023 acquired from Sentinel-2 L1C (Copernicus Browser) with 7m/px resolution have been downloaded.

Furthermore, in collaboration with Fiorentino-Ermini research team, we performed the high-resolution UAV-based mapping of the two active landslides (labelled Fosso Caforchio and Balzo del Prete landslides) distinguished on the left side of the valley. The drone flights were carried out in May and October 2024.

The monitoring of the Fiumarella di Corleto landslide was conducted using Unmanned Aerial System (UAS)-based photogrammetry, which enabled the capture of detailed images suitable for the creation of high-resolution Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) and orthophotos of the area under investigation. The UAS used for this study was a DJI Mavic 2 Pro, manufactured by Dà-Jiāng Innovations in Shenzhen, China. This system was equipped with a Hasselblad digital camera featuring a 20-megapixel resolution, a focal length of 24 mm (35 mm format equivalent), and an on-board Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) to ensure accurate geolocation of the captured imagery.

The data acquisition process required favorable meteorological conditions, specifically wind speeds below 15 km/h, to maintain flight stability and ensure high-quality image capture. To survey the approximately 1.5 km² study area comprehensively, two acquisition campaigns were conducted on May 23, 2024, and October 10, 2024. Given the considerable size of the area, the survey was divided into five remote flights, each pre-programmed with specific flight paths and take-off points. The missions were designed to achieve a consistent average flight altitude of 120 meters and incorporated a 70% frontal and side overlap between images.

Ground Control Points (GCPs) played a pivotal role in the georeferencing and orientation of the 3D model generated during the photogrammetry process. A total of 25 GCPs were distributed

strategically across the survey area. These points were represented by PVC markers measuring 0.6 m × 0.6 m, secured to the ground with metal hooks to prevent displacement. Their coordinates were precisely measured using a differential GNSS technique with a GCX3 Sokkia receiver operating in Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) mode. This approach ensured an average accuracy of approximately 0.01 meters.

The imagery captured during the UAS flights, comprising around 1,000 frames per campaign, was processed using Agisoft Metashape software (version 1.7.6). This software employs Structure-from-Motion (SfM) techniques to reconstruct a 3D model of the terrain by analyzing overlapping photographs. GCP data were incorporated during the processing phase to optimize the alignment of images by refining the estimated camera positions. Of the 25 GCPs, 20 were utilized for orientation during the bundle block adjustment process, while the remaining points were designated as check points (CHKs) to calculate the root-mean-squared error (RMSE) of the 3D model. The analysis yielded an RMSE of approximately 0.01 meters for GCPs and about 0.20 meters for CHKs, demonstrating the accuracy of the model.

Fig. 3 - Example of proper distributed GCP to georeferenced the SfM products.

From the high-density 3D point cloud generated during the SfM process, with a density of 120 to 130 points per square meter, various models were derived. These included a Digital Surface Model (DSM) with a resolution of 10 cm per pixel, a high-resolution orthomosaic at 5 cm per pixel, and a

Digital Terrain Model (DTM) with a ground resolution of 0.1 meters by 0.1 meters. The DTM was produced through an automatic filtering process to identify and exclude points corresponding to vegetation, such as trees and shrubs. These outputs were subsequently exported as raster files and further analyzed using QGIS software.

The detailed products generated through photogrammetric processing facilitated an in-depth geomorphological survey of the landslide area. By analyzing high-resolution orthophotos and a shaded relief map derived from the DSM raster data, it was possible to delineate the boundaries of the landslide and map its primary surface features with precision. This approach underscores the efficacy of integrating UAS technology and advanced photogrammetry techniques in the study of complex geomorphological phenomena like landslides.

The images obtained were used to perform a detailed geomorphological study of the two landslides. Geological field data mapped and UAS-images have been processed and implemented in a GIS environment using QGIS package. In addition, Information from the existing IFFI and PAI landslide databases was acquired for the entire catchment area of the Fiumarella di Corleto. Coordinates frame of the maps are expressed in: WGS 1984 UTM Zone 33N (EPSG:32633) and indicated at the margins of the maps sheet.

Results

Geological map

The geological map (format A0 - ISO 216) with an extension of about 50 km², consists of the main map and a legend. The nomenclature of the bedrock formations was adopted according to the paper by Giannandrea et al. (2016). The geological survey made it possible to distinguish sediments belonging to different geological formations composed mainly of clayey sediments of Cretaceous-Quaternary in age referable to the Argille Variegata Group, Gorgoglione and Sant'Arcangelo basins units and numerous landslide bodies with different levels of activity (fig. 4). Some of these extend to the valley floor of the fiumarella, temporarily obstructing the flow of water.

Argille variegata Group

The unit outcrops in the southern half of the catchment and groups the lower Varicolour clays, Sant'Arcangelo, and Upper Varicolour clays formations Cretaceous-Oligocene in age. The Lower Varicolour clays Formation made of red and green clays with lenses of siliceous calcilutites, marly limestones, sandstones and manganese siltstones. Usually the calcilute and calcarenitic levels thicken upwards. The clays are often flaked and chaotic, as a result of intense tectonization. The formation gradually passes upwards to the Monte Sant'Arcangelo Formation; the boundary is characterized by the progressive increase in limestone-marl-arenitic beds. The thickness of this formation can be estimated between 100-200 meters.

Fig. 4 – Geological map of the Fiumarella di Corleto catchment.

The Monte Sant'Arcangelo Formation is composed of a cyclic alternation beds of grey or whitish marly limestone with conchoid fracture, in layers varying in thickness from a few centimeters to several meters, of greenish-grey or reddish-brown clays, of grey laminated intraclastic calcarenites, with prismatic fracture and centimetric thickness, and of subordinate graded carbonate arenites, of grey-green color. Petrographically, calcilutites are biomicrites, calcarenites consist of packstone-wackestone made of laminated planktonic foraminifera, while the coarser lithotypes contain clasts with Solenoporaceae and macroforaminifera of the genera *Orbitoides* and *Siderolites*. Maximum thickness cropping out in the map about 150 meters. At the top some tens meters of brown marly clays with decimetric beds intercalations of marly limestones of the Upper Varicolored clays Formation.

Gorgoglione Basin

The basin fill consists of a succession (~2,150 m thick) with ages constrain referred from the upper part of Zone MNN4a at the Burdigalian/Langhian boundary to the Upper Tortonian zonal interval MNN11b (Giannandrea et al., 2016). The succession according to Giannandrea et al. (2016) can be subdivided, into the Val Miletta Formation and Gorgoglione Supersynthem (fig. 5). The lowermost Val Miletta Formation including more lithological members made of Numidian-like quartzarenites, Gorgoglione-like fine-grained turbidite sandstones, and, at the top of the formation, chaotic deposits of varicoloured clays, with mega block of calcarenites and calcareous marls lithologies. The Gorgoglione Supersynthem is subdivided into Cirigliano, that group the Ponte della Vecchia, Pozzo del Pellegrino, and Pietra del Corvo subsynthem, and Castelmezzano synthem (fig. 5). The three subsynthem are fining and thinning-upward turbidite successions, with conglomerate alternated to coarse-grained sandstone at the base and mudstone with thin beds of fine-grained sandstones at the top. The Castelmezzano Synthem show three vertical lithological variations bounded by two surfaces parallel to the above and below beds (figs. 5d, e, and f). The lowermost lithofacies made of about 260 m thick sandy mudstones with isolated lenses-shaped metric intercalations of pebbly sandstones. At the base of the lithofacies two coeval bodies, cropping out into two distinct areas located in the Castelmezzano-Pietrapertosa and Gorgoglione sectors. The two bodies consist of amalgamate beds of coarse-grained turbidite sandstones with pebbles and mud clast laterally interbedded with fine-grained facies. Between Castelmezzano and Pietrapertosa villages, in the upper part of the body, the coarse-grained sediments fill four submarine channel-shaped surfaces (~1 km wide), in a southeastwardly lateral offset stack. The intermediate lithofacies consist of ~450 m thick fining- and thinning-upward sandy mudstones with in the lower portion isolated lenses-shaped metric intercalations of chaotic mudstone beds. At last, in the uppermost lithofacies ~400 m thick fine laminate mudstones with intercalation of fine-grained turbidite sandstone in thin lenticular beds and high lateral continuity tabular bed-set, 1-5 m thick, of very fine-grained, mm-thick plane-parallel laminae contourites beds (Giannandrea et al., 2016). Age constrain of the stratigraphic units recognized in the Gorgoglione sedimentary basin fill are reported in the figure 5b.

Fig. 5 – Geological map (a) and stratigraphic section (b) of the northeast sector of the Gorgoglione Basin, (c) geological cross-section, across the Montagna del Caperino and Monte Impiso ridges, and (d, e, and f) panoramic views of the northeast boundary of the Gorgoglione Basin: d) view to the south from the Gorgoglione village, e) view to the south from the Pietrapertosa village, and f) view to the north from the Castelmezzano village.

In the study area outcrops chaotic varicolored clays, with blocks (interpreted as olistostrome) of the uppermost member of the Val Miletta Formation and fine-grained sediments of the Castelmezzano Synthem and Pietra del Corvo Subsynthem. Only at the top of the ridges along the southwester and northeaster boundaries of the river basin coarse-grained deposits are present. Along the southwest boundary outcrop sandstone with bed intercalations of calcilutites, marls and calcarenite of the Corleto Subsynthem, with at the top about 100 m thick sandstones of the Tempa Lata Subsynthem.

Pliocene-Quaternary units of the Sant'Arcangelo Basin

The units, made manly of sandstone deposits and subordinately of grey-blue marly-clays, outcrop in small areas only in the southern portion of the basin above the Lower Varicolored clays Formation.

Fosso Caforchio and Balzo del Prete landslides

The geomorphological work carried out in the field and through the use of 3D (DTM and DSM) images UAV-derived, made it possible to recognize two extensive landslides on the left side of the Fiumarella di Corleto valley. The two landslide made of structureless grey clay with angular clasts and block ranging in size from some cm to 2-3 m interpreted as debris flow deposits, with the accumulation area located for the two landslides into the thalweg of the river. The supply area of the Fosso Caforchio landslide is identified on the clayey sediments of the Pietra del Corvo Subsynthem at an altitudes of 950-1,100 m a.s.l., whereas, the supply area of the of Balzo del Prete landslide is identified between the altitudes of 1,000 and 1,180 m a.s.l., in the sandstones of the Castelmezzano Synthem (figs 4 and 6). Both landslides areas are 0,10 km-wide and about 2 km-long territory developed between the altitudes of 1,050 and 750 m a.s.l.

Fig. 6 – Panoramic view of the left side of the Fiumarella di Corleto valley, showing the Fosso Caforchio and Balzo del Prete landslides.

References

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